

LEGAL FOUNDATIONS AND POWERS OF PROSECUTORIAL OVERSIGHT ON RAPID SEARCH ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: This article scientifically analyzes the role of prosecutorial oversight in ensuring the rule of law in Uzbekistan, particularly focusing on the legal basis and practical significance of prosecutorial supervision over bodies conducting operational-search activities (OSA). A review of dissertations, scientific and theoretical sources, and legal literature reveals that the essence of prosecutorial supervision over OSA, its organizational and legal mechanisms, and functions have not been sufficiently studied, which underscores the theoretical and methodological relevance of this topic.

Keywords: prosecutorial oversight, operational-investigative activities, legality, supervisory powers, prosecution authorities, human rights, legal regulation, independence of the prosecutor's office, legal foundations, state supervision, covert operations, legal mechanisms, legal reforms, rule of law, supervisory methods.

Prosecutorial oversight plays a crucial role in ensuring the rule of law in our country, particularly in overseeing the execution of laws by bodies conducting operational-search activities. Scientific research reveals that within the framework of prosecutorial oversight and operational-search activity theory, the concept and essence of prosecutorial oversight of operational-search activities are insufficiently substantiated among scholars. This highlights the theoretical and methodological relevance of this issue and the necessity for its fundamental study. The organization of prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of legislation by bodies carrying out operational-search activities is reflected in the opinions of both theoretical and practical scholars. Notably, scientists such as B.Kh. Pulatov, F.Kh. Rakhimov, V. Karimov, O.M. Madaliev, M.Z. Rajabova, and D.S. Davudova have made significant contributions in this field. Their research has greatly advanced the development of management theory in the prosecutor's office and the establishment of the legal foundations for prosecutorial activities.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, emphasized, "People can endure many things, but they cannot tolerate injustice. The prosecutor's office should play a major role in ensuring justice in society"¹.

¹ Электрон манбаа: <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/178>

It should also be noted that the ongoing reforms in the country lead to continuous improvement of legislation, as well as the system and structure of the prosecutor's office. This necessitates theoretical understanding and scientific analysis.

Prosecutorial oversight is an essential and integral part of implementing the main tasks defined in Article 2 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to M. Rustambaev, "Prosecutorial oversight is an activity carried out by specially authorized officials, namely prosecutors, on behalf of the state, aimed at timely detection and elimination of law violations, bringing culpable individuals to justice in accordance with the procedure established by law, thereby ensuring precise and uniform implementation of laws"².

Also, according to F. Rakhimov, "Prosecutorial oversight in Uzbekistan is a specific type of activity of the prosecutor's office, which carries out state activities. Prosecutorial oversight is an independent, distinct form of state activity"³. A.B. Komilov emphasizes that "prosecutorial oversight manifests itself not only in identifying and eliminating instances of law violation, but also in taking measures to prevent such occurrences"⁴. According to D. Mirazov, "prosecutorial oversight is an activity carried out on behalf of the state by prosecutorial bodies, which have special authority from the legislative branch. It involves monitoring the accurate and uniform implementation of laws and consists of a set of various actions"⁵.

A similar opinion was put forward by O. Madaliyev: "in the system of state legal institutions, the prosecutor's office is defined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan as a separate independent structure and does not depend on any branch of state power"⁶. Indeed, the prosecutor's office is not a branch of government, as it functions as a "single system of centralized bodies exercising oversight on behalf of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

As noted by the German lawyer Christian Heinisch, oversight of investigative activities "must have strict legal boundaries, since it is a covert activity that seriously infringes on human rights"⁷.

² Рустамбаев М.Х. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Конституцияси ва прокуратура: рисола/Маъсул муҳаррир: ю.ф.д., А.Х. Саидов.-Т.: ТДЮИ нашриёти, 2005.-Б.8-12.

³ Рахимов Ф.Х. Прокурор назорати ва фаолият йўналишлари: илмий-амалий мақолалар тўплами/ ю.ф.д. Т.А. Умаров умумий таҳрири остида.-Т.: "Ношир" нашриёти, 2008.-Б.87-94.

⁴ Комилов А.Б., Тадбиркорларни ҳуқуқий ҳимоя қилишга қаратилган қонунлар ижроси устидан прокурор назоратининг ташкилий ҳуқуқий асосларини такомиллаштириш. Автореф. дисс. юридик фан. фалсафа. докт. Т., Ўзбекистон Республикаси Бош прокуратураси академияси, 2020.-Б.17.

⁵ Миразов М.Д. Дастлабки тергов идоралари фаолияти устидан контроль ва назоратни такомиллаштиришнинг назарий, ташкилий ва процессуал жиҳатлари. Автореф. дисс. юридик фан. докт. Т., ИИВ академияси, 2016.-Б.52.

⁶ О.М.Мадалиев Прокурор назорати. Дарслик. Умумий қисм.-Т.: ТДЮИ нашриёти, 2009.-48 бет.

⁷ Heinisch, C. *Strafprozess und verdeckte Ermittlungen*. Berlin, 2017.

French lawyer Pierre Lascombe, on the other hand, evaluates prosecutorial oversight as a "middle institution between administrative and judicial oversight", since the prosecutor's office, while being part of the crime control system, simultaneously acts as a guarantor of human rights⁸.

Professor Julian Richards from the University of London in Britain assesses the involvement of a prosecutor or an independent oversight body in covert investigations carried out by external and internal intelligence agencies as a "guarantee of legal legitimacy"⁹.

As Sergio Marques, an expert from the Council of Europe, emphasized, since each process in the TQF affects human rights, prosecutorial supervision must be harmonized with international standards¹⁰.

American researcher Katherine Gardner (Harvard Law School) emphasizes that the use of artificial intelligence and big data in TQF is making prosecutorial oversight more complex¹¹.

As a result of analyzing the concepts presented by legal experts above, the following characteristics of oversight were specifically highlighted: 1. Oversight is carried out exclusively by specially authorized state bodies as established in the Constitution and laws. 2. The areas and scope of activities of the bodies and officials exercising oversight are regulated by special normative documents. Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prosecutor's Office"¹² According to the relevant articles of the Law, the prosecutor may exercise supervision only within the scope and area defined by their authority. Oversight of the execution of laws is carried out continuously. The objects of supervision can be individuals and legal entities, as well as officials. Supervision is carried out to prevent unlawful actions that may harm the interests of individuals, society, and the state.

It should be noted that prosecutorial oversight can be carried out at all stages of criminal proceedings - pre-investigation inquiry, preliminary investigation, and court proceedings. Currently, prosecutorial supervision over the execution of laws by bodies conducting operational-search activities has not been separated into a distinct branch as an independent area. In this regard, the content and essence of prosecutorial supervision over the activities of bodies conducting operational-search activities allow for clearly defining the specific tasks of this supervision, its independent subject and object of oversight, as well as the specific powers of prosecutors. Thus, prosecutorial oversight is a practical and purposeful

⁸ Lacombe, Pierre. *Le contrôle du parquet sur l'enquête secrète*. Paris, 2019.

⁹ Richards, Julian. *Intelligence Studies: A Critical Introduction*. London: Routledge, 2015.

¹⁰ Marques, Sergio. *Human Rights and Secret Surveillance Practices*. Council of Europe Report, 2020.

¹¹ Gardner, K. *AI, Predictive Policing and Legal Oversight*. Harvard Journal of Law & Technology, 2022.

¹² Ўзбекистон Республикаси "Прокуратура тўғрисида" ги Қонуни. Электрон манбаа: <https://lex.uz/docs/106197>

activity, the effective implementation of which requires the consistent application of appropriate measures and control mechanisms.

When organizing prosecutorial supervision, the following must be determined: the subject, i.e., the goals and objectives of the activity; to whom or what the activity is directed (object); who should carry it out (subject); within what legal boundaries the activity should be conducted (limits); the set of rights and obligations (general scope of authority); the structure of prosecutorial bodies and their interaction in carrying out activities (organization); what decisions, actions, measures and methods can be employed (means and methods). The main features of prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of laws on operational-search activities are closely interconnected and are defined by law. At the same time, each feature has a distinct and independent meaning and can change in connection with changes in relevant social relations, state structure, and legal order.

Scholars note that prosecutorial supervision over the implementation of laws on operational-search activities can be studied from two perspectives:

- 1) as a branch of law;
- 2) as a distinct type of state activity or a branch of prosecutorial supervision.

If we define prosecutorial supervision over operational-search activities in general terms as a branch of law, then in its essence it encompasses social relations that require special, legally specific regulation. Each branch of law has its own specific subject of legal regulation and a method of influencing the behavior of participants in legal relations. Furthermore, the presence of a special subject and method of legal regulation ensures the stability and clarity of the legal phenomenon as a branch of law. In general, the method of legal regulation in society is implemented by influencing individuals' behavior through a set of state legal norms.

The method of legal regulation is carried out through the state, which determines the necessary behavior of the participant in legal relations.

The following main methods are used in the mechanism of legal regulation: giving orders; permitting; prohibiting. Analysis of the legislation regulating the organization of the activities of the prosecutor's office shows that the indicated methods are used in the legal regulation of these relations. For example, the method of issuing an order is reflected in the legislation, according to which the issue of appointing and dismissing the Prosecutor General is defined by law. The authorization method is reflected in Articles 13, 22, and 25 of the Law, which specify the powers of the Prosecutor General and the prosecutor. The prohibition

method is applied in Article 5 of the Law: employees of the prosecutor's office are required to renounce membership in political parties for the period of their powers. Also, according to Article 43 of the Law, employees of the prosecutor's office cannot engage in other paid or gratuitous activities, except for scientific, pedagogical and creative activities. From this point of view, the law of prosecutorial supervision, like other branches of law, has a clear structure, in which the norms regulating prosecutorial supervision over operational-search activities are of great importance.

In our opinion, prosecutorial supervision over operational-search activities is an independent supervisory and disciplinary mechanism carried out on behalf of the state, aimed at ensuring legality in the covert activities of operational bodies within the limits of the powers strictly defined by law, preventing possible violations of human rights, and assessing the legality of operational-search measures.

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